

PEDvolution

Interoperable solutions to streamline
PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration

Deliverable 11.1

Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
**State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101138472.

The Swiss project participants received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

Document Summary Information

Grant Agreement No	101138472	Acronym	PEDvolution
Full Title	Interoperable solutions to streamline PED evolution and cross-sectoral integration		
Start Date	01/01/2024	Duration	36 months
Project URL	https://www.pedvolution.eu/		
Deliverable	D11.1 Communication and dissemination activities - Year 2		
Work Package	WP11 – Communication, Dissemination & further Exploitation (Year 2)		
Contractual due date	31/12/2025	Actual submission date	30/12/2025
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	SXS		
Responsible Author	Maria-Ioanna Pavlopoulou (SXS)		
Contributions from	Marina Laskari (INLE), Alemu Belay (SIN), Sašo Brus (OFFSET), Vicente Carabias-Hütter (WIN), Nikos Charitos (ICOM), Matthias Haase (ZHAW), Amin Kouti (VITO), Minna Kuivalainen (SIN), Ahmed Samir Hedar (SIN)		
Reviewed by	Alexander Deliyannis (SXS), Marina Laskari (INLE), Reda El Makroum (TUW)		

Copyright message

©PEDvolution Consortium 2025. This document comprises entirely original and unreleased content unless explicitly stated otherwise. Recognition of previously published material and the contributions of others has been expressed through suitable citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is permitted, with acknowledgment of the source.

Disclaimer

PEDvolution - This project has received funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON) under the GA No. 101138472. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The European Commission holds no responsibility for any potential utilisation of the information it contains. The information is presented "as is" with no assurance or warranty, whether explicit or implicit, regarding its suitability for any specific purpose. The user assumes sole responsibility and risk when using this information.

Revision history (including peer reviewing & quality control)

VERSION	ISSUE DATE	% COMPLETE ¹	CHANGES	CONTRIBUTOR(S)
v0.1	21/02/2025	5%	Table of contents	SXS
v0.2	26/02/2025	7%	Final table of contents	SXS, INLE, TUW
v0.3	17/11/2025	85%	First version of deliverable	SXS
v0.4	08/12/2025	100%	Integration of INLE input sections 4.2 & 4.3 & document review	INLE
v0.5	09/12/2025	100%	Minor comments integration	SXS
v1.0	23/12/2025	100%	QA check and preparation for submission	TUW, INLE

1 According to Project’s Quality Assurance Process

Table of Contents

1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
2	INTRODUCTION	10
2.1	Mapping the Project’s Outputs	10
2.2	Deliverable Overview and Report Structure	12
3	IMPLEMENTATION OVERVIEW	14
4	COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS & CHANNELS	16
4.1	Project Visual Identify and Templates	16
4.2	Printable Materials	17
4.3	Online Communication Channels & Resources	18
4.3.1	Website	18
4.3.2	Social media	22
4.3.3	News Alerts	27
4.3.4	GDPR-compliant contacts Database	28
4.3.5	Digital Presentation	29
4.3.6	Digital Gateways – Digital hubs	29
4.3.7	Publications	30
4.3.8	Advertorial Video	31
5	EXPERT COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES	32
5.1	Third-Party Events	32
5.1.1	Spotlight FM+ Conference	33
5.1.2	IEWT 2025	34
5.1.3	C4E Forum 2025	34
5.1.4	ChangeNow & Cities Mission Conferences	35
5.1.5	Clima World Congress	36
5.1.6	Joint Online Workshop	36
5.1.7	Sustainable Places 2025	37
5.1.8	DUT PED Conference	38
5.2	Cooperation with BRIDGE and other EU Initiatives	39
5.2.1	Liaison with EU Initiatives	39
5.2.2	Liaison with standardisation activities	43
5.2.3	Liaison with other EU projects	44
5.3	Capacity Building Activities from PED Co-Developers to Follower PEDs	46
6	KPIs OVERVIEW AND PROGRESS	49
7	UPDATED WORKPLAN	52
8	CONCLUSION	56
9	REFERENCES	57
	Annex I: NEWS ALERT ISSUES	58
	Annex II: MONITORING AND TRACKING TOOL	62

List of Figures

Figure 1: PEDvolution website – Results	20
Figure 2: PEDvolution website – Knowledge Sharing Corner	21
Figure 3: PEDvolution featured on InterPED’s website.....	22
Figure 4: PEDvolution LinkedIn page.....	24
Figure 5: PEDvolution LinkedIn visitors – top geographical locations.....	24
Figure 6: PEDvolution X(Twitter) account	25
Figure 7: PEDvolution BlueSky account.....	26
Figure 8: PEDvolution YouTube channel.....	27
Figure 9: News Alert Screenshot from recipients’ email - featuring the Open Call for Demonstrators..	28
Figure 10: Digital Presentation Screenshot.....	29
Figure 11: PEDvolution poster featured at the Spotlight FM+ Conference, Zurich, Switzerland.....	34
Figure 12: PEDvolution at the C4E Forum, Cavtat, Croatia.....	35
Figure 13: SIN representing PEDvolution during the joint online workshop.....	37
Figure 14: SXS representing PEDvolution at the Sustainable Places workshop.....	38
Figure 15: PEDvolution poster (ZHAW) at the DUT PED conference in Milan.....	38
Figure 16: Presentation of the Winterthur PED (WIN) at the 5th SCC Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Workshop in Barcelona.....	42
Figure 18: PEDvolution team (WIN, VITO) at the CINEA cluster meeting in Brussels.....	45
Figure 19: Joint presentation of PEDvolution and sister projects at the CINEA cluster meeting in Brussels.....	45
Figure 20: Thematic panel (led by SIN) on Community engagement & social innovation with knowledge gained from PEDvolution at the joint Building the Future of Energy workshop.....	46
Figure 21: PEDvolution presentation (INLE) at the at the joint Building the Future of Energy workshop.....	46
Figure 22: PEDvolution WP12 – Gantt Chart – Work Plan overview.....	52
Figure 23: PEDvolution Year 3 C&D&E activities – detailed Work Plan.....	55

List of Tables

Table 1: Terminology	7
Table 2: Adherence to Project’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	10
Table 3: PEDvolution LinkedIn visitors by industry.....	23
Table 4: PEDvolution 3 rd party events participation (Year 2).	32
Table 5: PEDvolution contribution to BRIDGE activities.....	39
Table 6: Onboarding of follower PEDs – Kick of meeting draft agenda.	47
Table 7: KPIs and Year 2 Cumulative Status.....	50

Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Table 1: Terminology.

ABBREVIATION TERM	DESCRIPTION
AIOTI	Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation
BMs	Business Models
C&D&E	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation
C&D&E Manager	Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Manager
CEN/TC 465	Technical Committee 465 Sustainable Cities and Communities
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
DRM	Demand Response Module
EG	Elektro Gorenjska (<i>Slovenian Project Partner – PED Manager</i>)
ESCOs	Energy Service Companies
ESG	Es-Geht!-Energiesysteme GMBH (<i>German Project Partner</i>)
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEK	Gorenjske Elektrarne (<i>Slovenian Affiliated Partner – PED Manager</i>)
ICOM	Intracom Telecom (<i>Greek Project Partner</i>)
INLE	Inlecom Innovation (<i>Greek Project Partner & Project Coordinator</i>)
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LB	Lead Beneficiary

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

Mx	Month x
NTNU	Norwegian University of Science and Technology (<i>Norwegian Project Partner</i>)
OFFSET	OFFSET Energy (<i>Slovenian Project Partner</i>)
PED	Positive Energy District
PED-RA	PED Readiness Assessment
PEN	Positive Energy Neighbourhood
PU	Public
RA	Readiness Assessment
RD&I	Research, Development & Innovation
SCC	Sustainable Cities Community
SEN	Sensitive
SERI	Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation
SIN	Smart Innovation Norway (<i>Norwegian Project Partner</i>)
SWW	Sww Wunsiedel Gmbh (<i>German Project Partner - PED Manager</i>)
SXS	Sympraxis Team (<i>Greek Project Partner & C&D&E Manager</i>)
Tx	Task x
TL	Task Leader
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
VITO	Flemish Institute for Technological Research
WG	Working Group
WIN	City of Winterthur (<i>Swiss Associated Partner - PED Manager</i>)
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
ZHAW	Zurich University of Applied Sciences (<i>Swiss Associated Partner</i>)

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable presents an overview of the communication, dissemination, liaison, and exploitation efforts undertaken during the 2nd year (January – December 2025) of the PEDvolution project. It evaluates progress and impact against the Key Performance Indicators defined in the Grant Agreement and further detailed in the project’s “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination” (D10.1).

During Year 2, PEDvolution built on the foundations established in the first year, focusing on actively disseminating emerging project results and enhancing engagement with a wider set of stakeholders. Within the scope of Work Package 11 «Communication and Dissemination (Year 2)», activities included the regular updating of project’s online communication channels-including the project website, LinkedIn, X (Twitter), Bluesky, and YouTube-ensuring continuous interaction with the target audience and broader dissemination of project outputs. By the end of Year 2, these channels had reached a substantially increased audience, supporting visibility of PEDvolution’s developing results.

Project partners actively participated in numerous EU-level, national, and regional events, presenting research outcomes, technical findings, and project methodologies and approaches. These efforts successfully engaged a diverse set of stakeholders-including energy service providers, prosumers, residents, local authorities, investors, research communities, standardisation initiatives, and the wider public-strengthening awareness of PEDvolution’s activities and fostering knowledge exchange across Europe. Notably, year 2 marked enhanced participation in workshops, conferences, and joint sessions with sister projects, supporting both knowledge exchange and collaboration in the Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) community.

Liaison activities also intensified in year 2 as public project results became available. PEDvolution strengthened its engagement with EU initiatives such as BRIDGE and relevant projects including INTERPED, HARMONISE and ASCEND. The project also began formal engagement with standardisation bodies, particularly CEN/TC 465 “Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities,” positioning PEDvolution to contribute to the development of European standards. These efforts have amplified the project’s impact by facilitating cross-project knowledge transfer and aligning outputs with broader European policy and standardisation frameworks.

Exploitation-oriented activities were initiated in year 2 under Work Package 11, including the identification and characterisation of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), early steps toward defining joint and individual exploitation strategies, and the preparation of replication and market analyses (addressed in deliverable D11.2 “KERs and characterisation”). These activities contribute towards the groundwork for the upcoming demonstration phase, when targeted exploitation strategies will be specified to maximise project impact and ensure the uptake of PEDvolution solutions in PEDs and other urban contexts beyond project completion.

Coordinated by SXS as the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Manager, PEDvolution partners collaborated effectively across all tasks, contributing to a successful implementation of foreseen activities. The structured approach to KPI monitoring, reporting, and partner engagement has enabled a clear assessment of progress, demonstrating that project targets are on track, have been met or already exceeded. A summary report on year 2 communication, dissemination activities-including interactions with other EU initiatives, networks, and projects- is provided in the following chapters. The achievements of this year establish a strong foundation for further intensifying dissemination, exploitation, and stakeholder engagement in the project’s final year.

2 INTRODUCTION

This deliverable provides a detailed overview of the communication and dissemination activities conducted during the project’s second year of implementation. More specifically, it presents the undertaken and completed tasks and assesses progress against the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) as defined in the project’s “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination” (D10.1) and the Grant Agreement.

The purpose of this document is to provide a clear overview of the status and achievements of Work Package 11 «Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 2)» (WP11) activities, highlighting accomplishments and challenges encountered, while ensuring effective planning of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (C&D&E) activities for the project’s final year.

2.1 Mapping the Project’s Outputs

This section maps PEDvolution’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed. The official deliverable title and task descriptions are provided in the «GA Component Title» and the «GA Component Outline» columns in [Table 2](#) below. The chapters where these outputs are detailed are indicated in the «Respective Document Chapter(s)» column, while the «Justification» column presents a brief overview of the activities reported.

Table 2: Adherence to Project’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
DELIVERABLE			
D11.1 Communication and dissemination activities – year 2	Report on year 2 C&D activities and Liaison with Bridge and other EU initiatives. (T11.1 and T11.3).	Chapters 2, 3, 4, 5	This report provides a summary of the communication and dissemination activities and efforts carried out during year 2. It also details the liaison efforts and collaborations established with BRIDGE/other EU initiatives and the capacity building activities. Chapter 5 presents an overview of progress against the defined KPIs.
TASKS			
T11.1 Communication of the project and Dissemination of results - year 2	ST11.1.1 EU dissemination events and networks. PEDvolution will leverage its partners' membership and participation in	Chapters 3, 4	Chapter 3 presents: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Updates on the project’s visual identity and templates. • Implementation progress/updates on the online communication channels including website, social media, news alerts,

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
	<p>relevant EU-level associations and other groupings to further develop its outreach network for dissemination of the project results. Participation to at least 2 EU-level events, is foreseen during year 2 of the project.</p> <p>ST11.1.2 National dissemination events and networks. Similarly, PEDvolution will leverage its partners' membership and participation in relevant national networks for dissemination of its results. Participation to at least 2 national events, is foreseen during year 2 of the project.</p> <p>ST11.1.3 Project online presence updates. Updates via the project website (including News Alerts), its social media accounts and relevant hubs will be regular throughout Year 2 of the PEDvolution project.</p> <p>ST11.1.4 Other communication material – Advertorial video. A 3-5' advertorial video will present the project in English, explaining PEDvolution's ambitions and preliminary results in the context of the EU's climate and energy</p>		<p>GDPR-database, project's digital presentation, publications, advertorial video and any additional material developed.</p> <p>Chapter 4 (sub-section 4.1) presents PEDvolution's participation in thematically aligned third-party events - both national and EU-wide - as participated by project partners.</p>

PROJECT GA COMPONENT TITLE	PROJECT GA COMPONENT OUTLINE	RESPECTIVE DOCUMENT CHAPTER(S)	JUSTIFICATION
	<p>goals. The video will be scripted and produced in-house by SXS, with content inputs from partners, to be recorded by a professional camera crew at a suitable physical meeting.</p>		
<p>T11.3 Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives</p>	<p>This task continues the liaison activities described in T10.2. In this phase of the project liaison activities will also allow to carry out capacity building from PED co-developers to those PEDs joining us through the “PED demonstrators call” (T8.3), where the “ambassadors” of PEDs will be invited to share their experience. PEDvolution will participate in the annual BRIDGE general assembly and contribute to the relevant Working Groups, annual work programme and related reports as required and exchange experiences and best practices with other projects.</p>	<p>Chapter 4</p>	<p>Chapter 4 (sub-sections 4.2.1, 4.2.2, and 4.2.3) provides a detailed overview of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The liaison activities carried out with EU initiatives (including BRIDGE, AIOTI, Annex83). • The liaison/cooperation activities that have been implemented with other thematically aligned EU projects – including the sister projects. • The planned activities regarding capacity building as part of the new PED’s integration process.

2.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The objective of this deliverable is to provide a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities implemented during year 2 of the PEDvolution project. It aims to showcase the achievements and to evaluate the progress made with respect to the defined KPIs and requirements as foreseen by the GA, the project’s Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination, as well as the planning described in D10.2 “Communication and dissemination activities – Year 1”.

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

Additionally, the deliverable specifies the C&D&E objectives, activities, and tasks for year 3, while addressing identified challenges and incorporating corresponding improvements.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1:** Executive Summary.
- **Chapter 2:** (Present Chapter) is an introduction to this report.
- **Chapter 3:** Provides an overview of the C&D&E objectives, and activities performed in year 2.
- **Chapter 4:** Details the communication and dissemination tools and channels updates, divided into 3 main sections: the project's visual identity and templates, the printable materials, and the online communication channels.
- **Chapter 5:** Describes participation in national and EU-level 3rd party events, including standardisation efforts and liaison with other EU initiatives and projects, as well as capacity building activities.
- **Chapter 6:** Reviews progress with respect to the initially defined KPIs and overall project objectives; while identifying the main achievements, challenges and remedial actions.
- **Chapter 7:** Presents the C&D&E objectives for year 3 and the updated work plan, including partners' expected contributions and roles.
- **Chapter 8:** Summarises the main achievements and sets goals for the upcoming year.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OVERVIEW

PEDvolution's communication objectives as defined in the project's "[Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination](#)"(D10.1), are detailed below:

- Raise public awareness and improve understanding about the potential of PEDs and their significant contribution towards achieving energy-efficient and sustainable buildings and districts.
- Inform and raise public awareness about the project, its expected results, and progress.
- Empower a positive opinion about the project on an EU-level to the wider public.

Dissemination and exploitation efforts aim to:

- Ensure the engagement and participation of stakeholders.
- Promote the adoption of the project's platform, tools, and solutions by the professional and scientific communities, as well as by the competent national authorities and agencies at the EU -level.
- Support the dissemination of the project's development.
- Pave the way for a successful commercial and non-commercial exploitation of the project outcomes.
- Encourage the dissemination and further exploitation of project results beyond its completion.

During the 2nd year of implementation, activities intensified across all strands of communication, dissemination, exploitation, and liaison. Building on the foundation established during the first year, efforts shifted toward actively disseminating project results, expanding stakeholder engagement, and preparing the ground for the demonstration phase and future exploitation potential. As the first substantive outputs of PEDvolution became publicly available, communication and liaison activities gained strategic importance, enabling a more targeted and evidence-based outreach approach.

The tasks under Work Package 11 and their subtasks were successfully executed in alignment with the project's work plan. The C&D&E Manager (SXS) continued to coordinate daily implementation activities, while ensuring a consistent approach to project communication, materials, and reporting. Regular updates of the internal KPI monitoring and tracking tool supported continuous reporting across all partners and ensured that year 2 activities were systematically documented. The tool remained fully aligned with the Horizon Europe reporting requirements, facilitating smooth preparation for periodic reporting.

During this period, PEDvolution's communication tools were actively used and developed. The project website and social media channels (LinkedIn, X(Twitter), Bluesky, YouTube) were regularly updated with news, publications, and event announcements, increasing the project's online presence and visibility. Communication materials -including brochures, infographics, and joint SCC-branded visuals- were distributed at EU-level and international events through the SCC stand, further amplifying the project's outreach. These efforts significantly broadened the project's audience and increased engagement across key stakeholder categories.

Dissemination activities became more substantial as research findings and intermediate results emerged, particularly within the technical Work Packages (WP) 3-7. Project partners actively participated in numerous EU-level, regional, and national events, presenting PEDvolution's progress and engaging technical, policy, and industry communities. By the end of year 2, PEDvolution had participated

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

in and contributed to a significantly expanded portfolio of scientific conferences, expert workshops, and thematic sessions, thereby enhancing visibility and fostering knowledge exchange.

Liaison activities strengthened considerably as well. Engagement and collaboration with EU initiatives -especially BRIDGE- became more focused as project outputs matured. PEDvolution partners also advanced cooperation with thematic EU projects such as INTERPED, HARMONISE, ASCEND, and TIP4PED, supporting mutual learning and alignment with projects at different stages of implementation. Importantly, Year 2 marked the beginning of PEDvolution’s liaison with CEN/TC 465 “Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities.” This positions PEDvolution to contribute to future European standards and reinforces the project’s commitment to long-term impact.

Stakeholder interactions expanded substantially, reaching target groups across all the categories defined in the Exploitation and Dissemination Plan. Project activities during Year 2 resulted in engagement with representatives from:

- Target Group 1: Energy and mobility service providers
- Target Group 2: Residents, energy consumers, and end users
- Target Group 3: Energy prosumers
- Target Group 4: PED developers and managers
- Target Group 5: PED investors
- Target Group 6: Local authorities and city planners
- Target Group 8: Standardisation bodies
- Target Group 9: Research and academia
- Target Group 10: Specialist Media
- Target Group 11: General public

All project partners contributed systematically to the implementation of Year 2’s C&D&E activities, fulfilling their roles as planned. SXS, as C&D&E Manager, collaborated closely with the Coordinator and T11.3 «Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives» task leader (INLE), the Quality Assurance Manager (TUW), WP Leaders, PED Managers, Solution Providers, and the wider consortium. Monthly Executive Board (EB) meetings and dedicated task-level exchanges facilitated smooth implementation and ensured continued alignment. While collaboration was strong, regular exchanges further optimised the timely preparation of communication materials (such as news alerts, posts, website articles) and improved effective responsiveness to dissemination opportunities.

Overall, year 2 activities significantly strengthened collaboration across partners. Joint event participation, increased use of standardised templates and materials, and shared engagement in liaison and standardisation mechanisms contributed to a cohesive project identity. These developments have not only supported the effective implementation of year 2 tasks but have also established a robust basis for the project’s intensifying communication, dissemination, exploitation, and stakeholder engagement activities in the upcoming demonstration phase.

4 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS & CHANNELS

This chapter presents updates regarding PEDvolution’s communication and dissemination tools and channels, providing an overview of their usability and added value during the project’s second year of implementation.

4.1 Project Visual Identify and Templates

The project’s cohesive visual identity and standardised templates for project materials and public results (as described in D10.1) have been applied by all partners during year 2 and will continue to be utilised until project completion. These include the project’s logo, colour palette, font and tagline, as well as the funding authorities’ logos and disclaimers required by the European Union (EU) commission and Swiss Secretariat for Education, Research, and Innovation (SERI).

The following templates, designed to support implementation and ensure a unified structure across project outputs and results, have significantly contributed to maintaining a consistent visual identity, thereby maximising project visibility and supporting organised and effective dissemination efforts. All relevant materials can be found on the PEDvolution common internal SharePoint and “Annex I” of [D10.2](#).

REPORT/DELIVERABLE TEMPLATE

All deliverables, particularly those intended for public dissemination (PU), to PEDvolution’s target audience, adhere to the template provided in the project’s “Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination” (D10.1). This clear and straight forward structure has proven particularly valuable in the presentation of project results for the project’s target audience. The same template is utilised for internal deliverables and reports (SEN).

In year 2 the following deliverables have been developed, conforming to the defined format:

- D3.1 “Cohesive toolchain for integrated modelling of PED via Digital Twin” (M24) – SEN
- D4.1 “PED readiness assessment methodology, calculation sheet and action plan for testing the PED Readiness Assessment” (M24) – PU
- D4.2 “PED Readiness Assessment Policy Strategy Roadmap” (M24) – PU
- D4.3 “Specifications and plan for testing and deployment of PEDvolution decision support guideline” (M24) – SEN
- D4.4 “PEDvolution decision support guideline application” (M24) – PU
- D5.1 “Energy manager flexibility models and algorithms” (M24) – SEN
- D5.2 “Sector coupling and flexibility exchange” (M24) – SEN
- D5.3 “User Interface for PED design and management” (M24) – SEN (*deadline extended*)
- D6.1 “Implementation of business model innovation tools” (M24) – SEN
- D6.2 “Social innovation and engagement tools for PEDs, first period of implementation” (M24) – SEN

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

- D7.2 “Energy market mechanisms” (M18) – SEN
- D7.3 “Data exchange platform and connection with EU Data Spaces” (M24) – PU (*deadline extended*)
- D8.1 “PEDs Monitoring and Verification Plan and Co-developer demos preparation” (M23) – PU (*deadline extended*)
- D8.2 “Demonstrator acquisition process” (M24) - PU
- D11.1 “Communication and dissemination activities” (M24) – PU (*present document*)
- D11.2 “KERs and characterisation” (M24) – PU
- D14.1 “Report on First Reporting Period Management Activities” (M18) – SEN

MEETING AGENDA AND MINUTES TEMPLATES

The project’s monthly EB and ongoing WP meetings have continued to systematically follow the respective templates provided in “Annex I” of the project’s [“Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination”](#). This approach has supported the planning and record-keeping of each meeting.

This procedure has proved beneficial to the project’s overall organisation and ensured that the main discussion points and decisions have been officially recorded and agreed upon by all participants. This documentation acts as a point of reference for past discussions, providing a standardised structure, contributing towards a more solid implementation approach and to the timely implementation of activities. As a result, the project is better positioned to meet its objectives and deliver impactful outcomes.

PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

The PowerPoint template for the project’s presentations has also been used as appropriate by project partners, ensuring consistency across all project communications. This has helped maintain a visually coherent style and effectively convey the core messages to the intended audiences.

NEWS ALERT TEMPLATE

The project’s news alert template has served as a framework for the creation of project’s bi-annual news alerts, which aim to inform PEDvolution stakeholders on project progress. The template provides a structured approach for the dissemination of project events and results, thereby informing the project’s target groups and stakeholders, in a clear and coherent manner. During year 2, four issues have been distributed; for further details, refer to [Section 4.3.3](#) below.

4.2 Printable Materials

The project’s printable materials - namely the brochure, poster, and roll-up banner - are publicly available on the [project’s website](#) in English and all official consortium languages (i.e. Dutch, French, Greek, German, Norwegian, and Slovenian). Throughout year 2, these materials have significantly contributed to informing target audience and stakeholders, thereby enhancing project’s visibility and outreach.

BROCHURE

During second year of project implementation, the project’s brochure has been widely disseminated to a diverse audience, through several in-house and 3rd party events, as detailed in [Table 4](#). Additionally,

892 copies have been downloaded from the project's website. This outreach has successfully engaged a broad spectrum of target groups including university students, field experts, industry business partners, innovators EU institutions representatives, regional and national authorities, civil society, researchers and international organisations amongst others.

POSTER

The project's poster has been showcased in high-level conferences such as the Spotlight FM+ Conference in Zurich, the DUT PED Conference in Milan and the C4E forum in Cavtat, Croatia (see [Sections 5.1](#), & [5.2](#)). Where appropriate, the initial template was modified to meet the events' guidelines and objectives. To date, 859 copies have also been downloaded from the project's website.

This outreach has contributed to raising awareness of the project among key stakeholders and target audiences, increasing engagement and reinforcing the project's visibility at both national and international levels.

ROLL-UP BANNER

The roll-up banner is primarily intended for use at targeted events, presentations and thematically relevant conferences. Given the active engagement of PEDvolution partners in dissemination activities, the banner has already been displayed in more than five targeted events or exhibitions in PEDvolution countries including Greece, Belgium, and Switzerland. Additionally, 804 copies of the roll-up banner have been downloaded from the project website, further extending its reach. For more details, regarding participation in 3rd party events, please refer to [Section 5.1](#).

4.3 Online Communication Channels & Resources

Online communication channels and resources have continued to play a central role in PEDvolution's communication and dissemination efforts during Year 2. They have significantly contributed to further enhancing project awareness, its objectives and preliminary results, while providing updates on ongoing activities and news to both targeted audiences and the wider public. By actively leveraging these channels, PEDvolution has maintained a strong online presence, strengthened collaboration with other EU projects, and fostered sustained engagement of key stakeholders across the EU.

In this context, the ongoing development and regular updating of the project website, social media platforms, news alerts, GDPR-compliant database, digital presentation, as well as posts in relevant digital hubs, scientific publications, and the project's the advertorial video have been instrumental in consolidating communication efforts and ensuring continuity, thereby supporting the achievement of Year 2 KPIs.

The main highlights for each online channel are summarised in the following subchapters.

4.3.1 Website

The PEDvolution [website](#), strategically structured with a limited number of sections - including a single-page «Home» with key information, a «News» section, and a «Results» section ([Figure 1](#))- has been regularly updated to reflect project progress, activities, and available results. In addition, a «Networking Corner» is to be introduced in early 2026 to showcase collaboration with sister and thematically relevant

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

projects (such as [INTERPED](#), [HARMONISE](#), and [ASCEND](#)), and EU initiatives such as the [Scalable Cities Community](#) and [BRIDGE](#). The «*Knowledge Sharing Corner*» is primarily designed to make knowledge, methodological approaches, and know-how available to demonstration participants.

During year 2, the website has been updated with respect to the following aspects:

- News and Events
- Results (public deliverables, materials, and open access scientific publications)
- Knowledge Sharing Corner
- Networking Corner (to be made public in early 2026)

The following finalised public deliverables have been made available in the «*Results*» section:

- Data exchange platform design
- Communication and dissemination activities – year 1

As well as the following open access publications (see also [Section 4.3.7](#)):

- Haase, M., & Ashworth, S. (2025). Best Practices of PEDs and its Replication Potential. In *REAL CORP 2025 Proceedings/Tagungsband*, 14–16 April 2025.
- M. Sharifi, A. Kouti, M. H. Shamsi, R. Guo and D. Saelens, “Propagating epistemic uncertainties in planning and design of energy efficient districts,” *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 130, p. 106520, Jul. 2025.

Furthermore, the following public deliverables, will be made available shortly:

- PED Readiness Assessment Methodology, Calculation sheet and Action Plan for Testing the PED Readiness Assessment
- PED Readiness Assessment Policy Strategy Roadmap
- PEDvolution Decision Support Guidelines Application
- PEDs Monitoring and Verification Plan and Co-developer demos preparation
- Communication and dissemination activities – year 2
- KERs and characterisation

During year 2, the «*News*» section has been updated monthly. Partners have actively contributed by providing information on their participation in third-party events and on developments from other thematically relevant initiatives of interest to the PEDvolution audience. To ensure broad partner engagement and to share not only project progress but also relevant updates from the consortium countries, SXS has monitored adherence to the initial timeline for input provision, as agreed in the project’s Dissemination and Exploitation Plan.

The Knowledge Sharing Corner has been developed by SXS in collaboration with SIN, who selected and provided useful information primarily for the follower PED demonstrators to be incorporated from the existing work undertaken primarily within WP6 «*PED Business & Social Innovation tools*».

To date, the most visited sections are the PEDvolution «*Home*» page and the sub-page «*News*». For information on the number of unique website visitors, please refer to [Table 7](#) in [Chapter 6](#).

Figure 1: PEDvolution website – Results.

PEDvolution Business model innovation tool

PED Business Model Innovation Tool Approach

PEDvolution is developing a user-centric PED Business Model Innovation Tool through a process of co-creation, co-development, and co-validation—grounded in a deep understanding of diverse PED contexts.

Engaging and brainstorming with PED managers is a crucial step toward the successful development and implementation of the **Business Model Innovation (BMI) tool**. To support this, the project has identified tailored business brainstorming tools to gather relevant insights from each PED.

Business Brainstorming Tools for PEDs

Various brainstorming business tools have been identified and implemented to collect all relevant data from each PED. These tools are essential for the effective planning and strategic development of PEDs, helping them innovate, adapt, and thrive in creating sustainable, energy-positive communities. In this context, the following tools have been identified and are being implemented:

- ▼ **SWOT analysis**

Considering the complex nature and different set-ups of PEDvolution's PEDs, a SWOT analysis (see the template in **Figure 1**) is used to understand the internal and external factors affecting the implementation of each PED. By considering a balanced view of positive and negative factors, the SWOT analysis will help to make a knowledge-based decision and provide in-depth insight to PED managers involved in PED problem-solving and decision-making activities.

A SWOT analysis allows for the identification of:

- **Strengths:** PED internal traits and available resources (energy assets, finance, and relevant infrastructure) supporting the PED initiative.
- **Weaknesses:** PED internal factors hindering the PED in achieving its goal and ambition.
- **Opportunities:** external factors in the PED initiative that can help to take advantage of.
- **Threats:** external factors of the PED initiative that the PED needs to be aware of and that need to be avoided or mitigated.

In the context of PEDvolution, the SWOT analysis is designed to be done in an interactive way where PED managers and relevant stakeholders are actively engaged.

The diagram shows a SWOT analysis template. It consists of two main horizontal sections. The top section is labeled 'INTERNAL FACTORS' and is divided into two columns: 'STRENGTHS (+)' on the left and 'WEAKNESSES (-)' on the right. The bottom section is labeled 'EXTERNAL FACTORS' and is divided into two columns: 'OPPORTUNITIES (+)' on the left and 'THREATS (-)' on the right. The entire template is enclosed in a thin black border.

Figure 1: SWOT analysis template.

Download Template

@ PEDvolution_BM SWOT template.pptx

Figure 2: PEDvolution website – Knowledge Sharing Corner.

Finally, PEDvolution is also showcased on the websites of several sister projects and related initiatives including the following:

- [InterPED](#)
- [Harmonise](#)
- [ASCEND](#)
- [Smart Cities Marketplace](#)
- [BRIDGE initiative](#)
- [COST Action PED-EU-NET](#)
- [ENLIT EU projects directory](#)

Figure 3: PEDvolution featured on [InterPED's website](#).

4.3.2 Social media

During Year 2, PEDvolution's social media presence - LinkedIn, X (Twitter), YouTube, and Bluesky - continued to play a key role in communicating project progress and results. Channels are managed by SXS and feature essential project information, progress, and news.

Throughout the second year, updates were published regularly, with each social media page counting 103 original posts since project launch. These accounts have attracted a total of 1115 followers, reflecting a steady increase in audience engagement and outreach. On average, three to four posts were published per month across platforms, featuring updates on project milestones, event participation, and relevant EU-level initiatives.

As in Year 1, partners contributed content for post development as appropriate, ensuring balanced representation of project activities and national perspectives. Analytics indicate that LinkedIn continues to be the most impactful platform for reaching PEDvolution’s target audience - mainly professionals, researchers, and policymakers active in the energy and urban innovation domains. The addition of the Bluesky account in Year 2 has further expanded PEDvolution’s online presence, complementing existing platforms and supporting broader engagement with new audiences and digital communities.

PEDVOLUTION LINKEDIN

Throughout the second year of implementation, the [PEDvolution LinkedIn page](#) (Figure 4) has maintained a high level of activity with 756 followers. Its performance exceeded the KPIs established for this period, as shown in [Table 7](#), reflecting strong engagement across key metrics, such as posts, impressions, followers, unique views and total page views.

The PEDvolution LinkedIn page continues to attract a diverse audience in terms of both demographic profile and geographical location. Stakeholders from a wide range of disciplines are actively engaging with the page, covering the project’s target groups. These include representatives from various industries including research services, environmental services, IT services and consulting, services for renewable energy, as well as architecture and planning. The total views per industry is represented in [Table 3](#).

In terms of geographical reach, PEDvolution’s partner countries - Greece, Germany, Slovenia, Switzerland, and Germany - remain among the top contributors. The project’s audience also extends beyond the partnership, reaching countries such as France and Israel (see also [Figure 5](#)). Each original post continues to achieve strong visibility, with an average of 990 impressions and an engagement rate of approximately 20%, reflecting the page’s effectiveness in reaching and engaging its target audience. Visitors by geographical location are presented in [Figure 5](#). Overall during year 2, LinkedIn posts reached a total of 56 574 impressions and 941 reactions. Additionally, the highest level of interaction was recorded during the publication and dissemination of the open call for PED demonstrators (May–June 2025).

Table 3: PEDvolution LinkedIn visitors by industry.

INDUSTRY	TOTAL VIEWS	PERCENTAGE (%)
Research services	318	46.2
Environmental services	58	8.4
Higher education	30	4.4
IT services and IT consulting	27	3.9
Services for renewable energy	25	3.6
Renewable energy equipment manufacturing	24	3.5
Technology, Information and Internet	18	2.6
Advertising services	17	2.5
Architecture and Planning	15	2.2
Business Consulting and Services	14	2
Others	143	20.7
Total	689	100

Figure 4: PEDvolution LinkedIn page.

Figure 5: PEDvolution LinkedIn visitors – top geographical locations.

PEDVOLUTION X (TWITTER)

[PEDvolution’s X \(Twitter\)](#) account has followed a similar approach to LinkedIn for launch and outreach, aiming to engage with the project’s target audience effectively. By the end of year 2 (M24), the account has attracted 200 followers, representing a slight increase compared with the previous year. Significant efforts by the C&D&E Manager, in collaboration with project partners, have supported the growth of reach and engagement. Targeted posts and shared content are published regularly, with each post receiving an average of approximately 100 views (see [Figure 6](#) for an illustrative example). Overall, however, X remains less impactful than LinkedIn in terms of reaching the project’s target groups.

Figure 6: PEDvolution X(Twitter) account.

PEDVOLUTION BLUESKY

Over the past period, a notable shift from X (Twitter) to Bluesky has continued, particularly among experts and professionals in environmental and energy-related fields. To adapt to this evolving digital landscape and enhance engagement with its target audience, PEDvolution continued to actively engage via its [Bluesky account](#) during Year 2 (see [Figure 7](#)). Operating alongside the X account, the Bluesky page allows the project to maintain its presence across multiple platforms while exploring new avenues for outreach and stakeholder interaction. As of M24, the Bluesky page has attracted 144 followers, as reported in [Table 7](#), reflecting the early stages of audience growth on this emerging platform.

Figure 7: PEDvolution BlueSky account.

PEDVOLUTION YOUTUBE CHANNEL

During year 2, PEDvolution’s [YouTube channel](#) (Figure 8) has been actively maintained as a key digital gateway for sharing project outputs and engaging with a wider audience. As of M24, the channel hosts five videos and has attracted five subscribers. The uploaded content includes:

- A promotional video, *PEDvolution at a Glance*
- PEDvolution’s advertorial video
- A recording from the joint online workshop *Building the Future of Energy: A Joint Workshop on PED Innovation and Collaboration*
- A recording of PEDvolution’s participation in the *2024 Sustainable Places Conference* (online paper session); and
- A recording from the *2025 Sustainable Places Conference* physical workshop, *Strategic Citizen Engagement and Impact in Positive Energy Districts*.

These videos serve as a central repository for project dissemination, ensuring visibility of PEDvolution’s activities, results, and stakeholder interactions, while supporting engagement across the consortium and beyond. During year 3, the content will be significantly expanded with additional recordings from project activities, workshops, conferences, webinars, and short videos from recorded interviews, and the project’s final EU conference, further enhancing outreach and visibility among key stakeholders and the broader public.

Figure 8: PEDvolution YouTube channel.

4.3.3 News Alerts

During year 2, PEDvolution published four News Alerts, continuing its efforts to provide concise and engaging updates to its target groups on project progress, key milestones, and upcoming events.

The first News Alert of the year ([Figure 9](#)), released in early May 2025 (M17), announced the launch of the [PEDvolution Open Call for Demonstrators](#) (T8.3), outlining its objectives, participation requirements, and opportunities. A follow-up issue at the end of the same month (M17), further promoted the Open Call, while simultaneously featuring the organisation of an up-coming joint online webinar with the Scalable Cities community projects, «*Building the Future of Energy: A Joint Workshop on PED Innovation & Collaboration*» (see [Section 5.2](#)).

The third issue, published in June 2025 (M18), marked the first biannual News Alert of 2025, providing a comprehensive overview of the project’s progress during the first half of the year. It presented updates from the technical work packages, preliminary results, scientific publications, and partners’ participation in major European events.

The fourth issue, released in November 2025 (M23), served as the second biannual News Alert of the year, summarising key achievements from the second half of Year 2, including the launch of the project’s advertorial video, enhanced cooperation with sister projects, participation in liaison activities, and preparation for Year 3.

All four News Alerts were disseminated electronically via the project’s “Stay in Touch” subscriber list - which, by the end of Year 2, had reached 143 subscribers, achieving open rate of 45%. The next bi-annual news alert is scheduled for June 2026 (M30).

Figure 9: News Alert Screenshot from recipients’ email - featuring the Open Call for Demonstrators.

4.3.4 GDPR-compliant contacts Database

The contacts database established in year 1 has been updated to include representatives from diverse target groups such as researchers, academics, entrepreneurs, regional and national public authorities, who have expressed interest in receiving updates on project progress and results.

The purpose of this database is to streamline and facilitate effective contact management in view of the project’s dissemination activities and support stakeholder engagement in upcoming activities. This engagement will be of particular importance during the co-development and testing phases (year 3), where active collaboration with these groups will play a key role in project progress.

The database is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as all listed individuals have expressed interest in the project either via the project’s website or from a one-to-one basis at 3rd party events or workshops, and have confirmed that they wish to receive relevant updates and information.

In year 3, during the piloting phase and WP9 «PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment», this list is expected to expand further, as stakeholders directly involved in the pilot testing activities will be asked to provide their consent to receive project updates through the relevant pilot participation form.

4.3.5 Digital Presentation

The project’s digital presentation ([Figure 10](#)), provides a comprehensive overview of PEDvolution, serving as a key tool for partners to communicate project activities and progress in 3rd party events. Following its initial design, the presentation has been updated twice (in October 2024 and May 2025), to incorporate the latest public results. It has been useful on multiple occasions as a basis for preparing materials presented at 3rd party events, such as joint webinars, workshops, and conferences (see [Section 4.1](#)).

Figure 10: Digital Presentation Screenshot.

4.3.6 Digital Gateways – Digital hubs

During Year 2, PEDvolution maintained an active presence on [BUILD UP](#), the largest European portal dedicated to knowledge sharing on energy efficiency and renewable energy in the building and construction sector. Four posts were published on the platform, highlighting the project’s profile, updates on the completion of the analysis phase and initial results:

- [PEDvolution project \(April 2025\)](#)
- [PEDvolution’s promising beginning: Completion of the analysis phase and first key outputs \(April 2025\)](#)
- [Call for demonstrators: Join PEDvolution in advancing interoperable solutions for Positive Energy Districts \(May 2025\)](#)
- [Joint online workshop on Positive Energy Districts \(June 2025\)](#)

The Open Call for demonstrators was also featured on the following targeted groups of the [Net Zero Cities platform](#):

- [Funding, opportunities and partnerships for cities](#)
- [NEUTRALPATH](#)

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

These contributions enhanced PEDvolution’s visibility within the EU energy efficiency community and fostered engagement with professionals and policy makers active in the field.

In parallel, PEDvolution has been registered on [Construction21](#), the international information network for sustainable construction professionals. More active use is foreseen in the project’s final phase. Below are some indicative topics for which short articles have been planned for publication during year 3, in line with PEDvolution’s progress and expected results:

- Introduction to the PEDvolution follower PEDs (open call results)
- PED readiness assessment: a policy strategy roadmap
- Planina residential neighbourhood: a developing PED within an industrial community
- The PEDvolution decision support guideline application
- The Schönbrunn village and the super-PED concept
- Stakeholder engagement within the Gemeinschaft Hard community in Winterthur
- The Strategic Role of Social Innovation in advancing Planning, Implementation, and Monitoring of Positive Energy Districts
- Interoperable Digital Platforms for Positive Energy Districts: Enabling Data-Driven Decision Making

Throughout the project duration, at least 10 posts are expected to be published across the respective digital gateways, ensuring continuous dissemination of knowledge and project outcomes to stakeholders across and beyond the EU, with at least 6 of these planned for the project’s final year.

4.3.7 Publications

PEDvolution’s 2025 publications played a central role in highlighting the project’s emerging insights, methodologies, and early findings across scientific and academic communities. These targeted contributions ensured broad visibility and further strengthened the project’s position within the evolving Positive Energy Districts landscape.

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

During year 2, the project has published three open-access scientific papers, which are also available on the project’s [Zenodo](#) open-access repository, along with the project’s public deliverables:

- [1] [M. Haase, “Entschlüsselung des Dekarbonierungsprozesses von Quartieren aus Betreiber- und FM-Sicht,” in SPOTLIGHT FMplus – Facility Management Fachkonferenz: Wissenschaft und Praxis im Dialog, Tagungsband, Zürich, Switzerland, 30–31 Jan. 2025.](#)
- [2] [Haase, M., & Ashworth, S. \(2025\). “Best Practices of PEDs and its Replication Potential”, in REAL CORP 2025 Proceedings/Tagungsband, 14–16 Apr. 2025.](#)
- [3] [M. Sharifi, A. Kouti, M. H. Shamsi, R. Guo and D. Saelens, “Propagating epistemic uncertainties in planning and design of energy efficient districts,” Sustainable Cities and Society, vol. 130, p. 106520, Jul. 2025.](#)

In addition, the project contributed towards the following publication in a subscription-based journal:

- [1] [Conte, V. Carabias, L. Berzi, P. Kienast, M. Delogu, “Positive energy district evolution: A test case for Winterthur’s Hard Community,” Journal of Smart Cities and Society, vol. 4 no. 3, 2025](#)

Over the course of the project, PEDvolution aims to publish a total of at least 5 scientific papers, thereby actively contributing towards the advancement of knowledge and dissemination of its research outcomes. At least 2 more scientific publications are expected.

POPULARISED PUBLICATIONS

Furthermore, PEDvolution has been featured in several popularised and outreach publications, as listed below:

- [Project description in BRIDGE Brochure 2025](#)
- [SCC February newsletter D7.1 reference](#)
- [Article in SXS newsletter & website «The PEDvolution consortium meets in Kranj, Slovenia»](#)
- [Scalable Cities Community News - May 2025 – PEDvolution Open Call for PED demonstrators](#)
- [Smart Cities Marketplace - Open Call for PED demonstrators](#)
- [Article in SXS newsletter & website «PEDvolution AND oPEN Lab JOINT PRESENCE AT C4E FORUM 2025»](#)
- [ESG article on website «The PEDvolution consortium meets in Kranj, Slovenia»](#)
- [From data to decisions: Key lessons from the SCC projects](#)

4.3.8 Advertorial Video

PEDvolution's [advertorial video](#) has been developed, refined, and uploaded to the project's official YouTube channel in October 2025 (M22). The video was produced in-house by SXS, with valuable contributions from consortium partners. Short interviews were recorded by a professional camera crew with SIN, INLE, ICOM, WIN and OFFSET, while online interviews were conducted with ICOM, SWW, ESG, EG, GEK, ZENOB, VITO and ZHAW. The video's aim objective is to showcase PEDvolution's goals, PED co-developer sites, and solutions, serving to act as a key communication asset for future outreach and visibility efforts.

Subtitles are available in English and all partnership languages (Dutch, French, Greek, German, Norwegian, and Slovenian), to ensure accessibility and inclusiveness across the consortium countries. The video has been promoted through the PEDvolution and partners' social media channels, as well as features in the project's latest News Alert issue to reach maximum visibility. Dissemination efforts will continue over the coming months. Currently, the video has received 141 views.

5 EXPERT COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

5.1 Third-Party Events

Building on the solid engagement established during the first year, PEDvolution continued to maintain a strong external presence in Year 2, participating in 17 third-party events. These activities played a key role in broadening the project’s visibility, fostering knowledge exchange, and creating new opportunities for collaboration within the Positive Energy District research community. Through these participations, the consortium effectively engaged a diverse range of stakeholders and reinforced connections across the PED ecosystem. [Table 4](#) below provides an overview of these events, as recorded in the C&D&E Activities Tracking and Monitoring Tool (see [Chapter 5](#)).

Table 4: PEDvolution 3rd party events participation (Year 2).

NO.	EVENT	DATE(S)	CITY/AREA	COUNTRY	NATIONAL/ EU-LEVEL	PARTICIPATING PARTNER	ATTENDEES
1	Spotlight FM+	30-31/01/2025	Zurich	Switzerland	National	ZHAW	180
2	IEWT 2025	26-28/02/2025	Vienna	Austria	EU	TUW	40
3	Scalable Cities Community Roadshow P2P event “How to Deploy Innovative Financial Strategies to Unlock Private Investment for Climate Transition Projects”	27-28/03/2025	Barcelona	Spain	EU	WIN	50
4	Real Corp	14-16/04/2025	Graz	Austria	EU	ZHAW	120
5	ChangeNOW conference	24-26/04/2025	Paris	France	EU	SXS (via SCC)	n/a
6	Cities Mission Conference	06-08/05/2025	Vilnius	Lithuania	EU	SXS (via SCC)	900
7	Huawei ICT Day 2025	14/05/2025	Dübendorf	Switzerland	National	ZHAW	200
8	C4E Forum	20-23/05/2025	Cavtat	Croatia	EU	SXS	230
9	EEM 25	27-29/05/2025	Lisbon	Portugal	EU	TUW	25
10	Clima World Congress	04-06/06/2025	Milano	Italy	EU	ZHAW	580
11	Joint online workshop “Building the Future of Energy: A Joint Workshop on PED Innovation	11/06/2025	Online	-	EU	INLE, SIN	47

NO.	EVENT	DATE(S)	CITY/AREA	COUNTRY	NATIONAL/ EU-LEVEL	PARTICIPATING PARTNER	ATTENDEES
	<i>and Collaboration”</i>						
12	Scalable Cities Community Roadshow, “Nature, Mobility, and Urban Sustainability: European Cities Towards Climate Neutrality”	14-15/07/2025	Athens	Greece	EU	SXS	45
13	CINEA Cluster meeting on PENs & PEDs	29/09/2025	Brussels	Belgium	EU	VITO, WIN	30
14	Sustainable Places 2025 - workshop	08-10/10/2025	Milan	Italy	EU	SXS	26
15	Central Europe towards Sustainable Building 2025	16-19/09/2025	Prague	Czech Republic	EU	VITO, ZHAW	130
16	PED DUT Conference	01-03/10/2025	Milan	Italy	EU	ZHAW	120
17	Workshop on Energy Poverty	3-4/12/2025	Athens	Greece	National	SXS	40

The total number of individuals reached through these activities is detailed in [Table 7](#).

The following section provides an overview of the scope and participation objectives of notable EU-level and national events previously mentioned.

5.1.1 Spotlight FM+ Conference

The Spotlight FM+ Conference, co-organised by ZHAW Zurich University of Applied Sciences, the [International Facility Management Association](#) (IFMA) Switzerland Chapter, and the German Association for Facility Management (GEFMA), took place in Zurich on 30–31 January 2025. Bringing together over 180 key stakeholders from academia, industry, and policy-making across the DACH (Germany, Austria, and Switzerland) region, the event provided a vital platform for exchanging insights on innovative solutions and emerging trends in facility management and real estate. The conference featured two distinct focus areas: an industry-focused Spotlight day and a research-driven FMplus day, fostering dynamic discussions on advancements in the field.

PEDvolution was disseminated through a dedicated poster presentation, which highlighted the project’s vision to transform urban environments via sustainable energy integration and the development of its innovative digital solutions. Expert discussions were held on specific aspects of PED assessment with the facility management industry, raising awareness of PEDvolution’s objectives and expected results among EU-wide target groups. The dissemination demonstrated how the project supports the evolution of positive energy districts and contributes to Europe’s goal of carbon-neutral neighbourhoods, districts, and cities by 2050.

Figure 11: PEDvolution poster featured at the Spotlight FM+ Conference, Zurich, Switzerland.

5.1.2 IEWT 2025

The 14th International Energy Economics Conference (IETW) was held between 26–28 February 2025 in Vienna, Austria. The conference brought together leading experts, researchers, and industry representatives to discuss developments in energy markets, demand-side management, and innovative solutions for the European energy transition.

With the participation of TUW, PEDvolution’s scientific research was disseminated through a dedicated presentation within the session “Endconsumers”, highlighting work carried out under Task 5.1: «DRM (Demand Response Module) Optimisation, Energy and Flexibility Management.» The presentation, titled “Reinforcement Learning-Based Charging Control in Households under Real-Time Pricing”, showcased advanced methodologies for optimizing household energy consumption and flexibility, demonstrating the technical innovation and practical applicability of PEDvolution solutions.

This dissemination offered an opportunity to engage with experts from academia, industry, and policy, raising awareness of PEDvolution’s progress, promoting knowledge exchange, and highlighting the project’s contributions to enabling efficient, data-driven management of energy within Positive Energy Districts.

5.1.3 C4E Forum 2025

On May 22nd, during the [Knowledge Hub Poster Session](#) at the C4E Forum in Cavtat, Croatia, PEDvolution and [oPEN Lab](#) were jointly disseminated in a thematic session on “Multi-Level Innovation

in Positive Energy Neighbourhoods and Districts.” The session explored how Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) and Positive Energy Neighbourhoods (PENs) contribute to the energy transition, highlighting both shared and distinct project approaches and demonstrating how digital, interoperable, and scalable solutions can enable real-world energy-positive outcomes. By leveraging integrated data, ICT frameworks, and collaborative governance models, the projects showcased pathways for European communities to move beyond pilots and living labs toward tangible implementation.

Particular attention was given to the Planina neighbourhood in Kranj, Slovenia -PEDvolution’s co-demonstrator and a key geographical focus in Central and South-Eastern Europe- one of the sites where project solutions are developed and tested. The session also provided an opportunity to disseminate PEDvolution’s Open Call for PED demonstrators, which aimed at onboarding additional PEDs across Europe ready to test and showcase the project’s innovative solutions and methods. Overall, the session underscored the value of cross-project collaboration, real-world experimentation, and open innovation in accelerating Europe’s clean energy transition, while inviting new stakeholders to engage with PEDvolution through its ongoing Open Call.

Figure 12: PEDvolution at the C4E Forum, Cavtat, Croatia.

5.1.4 ChangeNow & Cities Mission Conferences

PEDvolution leveraged its involvement in the Scalable Cities and Communities (SCC) initiative (see [Section 5.2.1.5](#)), and particularly its active participation in the Communication and Dissemination Task Group, to ensure strong visibility across key European innovation events.

Dissemination was carried out through the SCC stand, where PEDvolution was featured alongside other SCC projects. This presence was supported by a range of project dissemination materials, including brochures, infographics, and joint SCC project infographics, which highlighted shared objectives and complementary activities. Through this coordinated setup, PEDvolution was showcased at two key international events: i. [ChangeNow](#), in Paris, and ii. the [Cities Mission Conference](#), in Vilnius.

These events offered important opportunities to reach diverse audiences, raise awareness of PEDvolution’s objectives and progress, and reinforce the project’s visibility within both the SCC network and the broader EU Mission ecosystem.

5.1.5 Clima World Congress

On 5 June 2025, during the Clima World Congress -which gathered 580 participants from diverse target groups, including industry, business partners, innovators, EU institutions, national, regional, and local authorities, civil society, citizens, research communities, international organisations, specific end-user communities, and investors- a targeted session on PEDs and energy communities was held, titled “Positive Energy Districts and Energy Communities: Case Studies and Applications Towards the Decarbonisation of the Built Environment”. The session was chaired by ZHAW, providing a platform to share and discuss the latest insights from PED research and implementation.

ZHAW disseminated findings from WP4 «PED Readiness Assessment» and recent insights from PED research was shared and discussed. The project’s contributions emphasised the integration of technical solutions with community-driven approaches, demonstrating how energy communities and PEDs can support sustainable urban decarbonisation. Key outcomes included networking opportunities, knowledge exchange, and the dissemination of PEDvolution’s approaches, results, and methodologies, reinforcing the project’s visibility and fostering future collaboration on an international, regional and local levels.

5.1.6 Joint Online Workshop

On 11 June 2025, PEDvolution participated in the joint online workshop “Building the Future of Energy,” co-organised with four leading Horizon Europe PED projects - [InterPED](#), [ASCEND](#), [HARMONISE](#), and [NEUTRALPATH](#) - in cooperation with the [Scalable Cities Initiative](#). Designed for researchers, built-environment professionals, prosumers, and citizens, the event provided an interactive forum for sharing experiences, exchanging tools, and strengthening collaboration on the development and implementation of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs). [Figure 13](#) presents a representative screenshot captured during the event session.

The agenda included project presentations, a joint session on cross-project synergies and the role of Scalable Cities, and expert-led discussions on key PED topics. Representing PEDvolution, Marina Laskari presented the PEDvolution project while Minna Kuivalainen presented the project’s approach to social innovation and community engagement (WP6 T6.2 «Social innovation tool co-development and implementation»), emphasising the importance of local context, participatory processes, and the principle that PEDs must “work technically and matter locally.” The discussion highlighted shared challenges, diverse local realities, and strong opportunities for replication, mutual learning, and deeper cooperation across the European PED ecosystem. The full [webinar recording](#) is available on PEDvolution’s YouTube channel.

Figure 13: SIN representing PEDvolution during the joint online workshop.

5.1.7 Sustainable Places 2025

In October 2025, PEDvolution participated in the *Sustainable Places 2025* conference held in Milan, Italy, co-organised by R2M Solution and the Comune di Milano. Within this leading European forum on sustainable urban transformation, the project co-organised and contributed to the workshop “*Strategic Citizen Engagement and Impact in Positive Energy Districts*”, alongside eight sister initiatives, including InterPED, TIPS4PED, ARV, COMMUNITAS, Citizen-led Renovation, NEUTRALPATH, LEGOFIT, and ASCEND. Represented by SXS, PEDvolution delivered the presentation “*Empowering PED Innovation: Building on a Tradition of Local Stakeholder Engagement*”, highlighting the project’s participatory approach and methodologies for fostering inclusive PED ecosystems. The workshop explored how citizen engagement, digital tools, and social innovation complement technological advances in the creation of Positive Energy Districts. [Figure 14](#) provides a screenshot captured during the event. The session fostered active knowledge exchange and collaboration among EU projects, reaffirming that Europe’s energy transition is both technological and societal - driven by communities co-creating resilient and sustainable urban futures. This collaboration will lead to the submission of a joint paper to the conference’s organising committee in December 2025.

Figure 14: SXS representing PEDvolution at the Sustainable Places workshop.

5.1.8 DUT PED Conference

ZHAW presented the PEDvolution results with a poster (Figure 15) in the DUT PED conference that took place in Milan on 1-3 October 2025. The conference was attended by 150 participants from different backgrounds/professions reaching from academia to municipalities and solution providers.

Figure 15: PEDvolution poster (ZHAW) at the DUT PED conference in Milan.

5.2 Cooperation with BRIDGE and other EU Initiatives

As part of a dedicated project task (T11.3) PEDvolution establishes connections, fosters collaboration, and exchanges knowledge with several important initiatives, projects and activities. These were well identified at the outset of PEDvolution, and connections were established over the first year of the project, as detailed in Deliverable 10.2 Communication and dissemination activities – Year 1.

In this section the continuation of this cooperation in Year 2 is documented.

5.2.1 Liaison with EU Initiatives

The project is engaged in a number of EU initiatives such as BRIDGE, Scalable Cities and ETIP-SNET. In Year 2 a number of meaningful exchanges were performed with the first results of the PEDvolution solutions co-development and barriers and lessons learned so far by the project PEDs.

5.2.1.1 BRIDGE

The project is engaged in all four Working Groups of BRIDGE:

1. Regulation (represented by INLE)
2. Data Management (represented by ICOM)
3. Business Models (represented by SIN)
4. Consumer and Citizen Engagement (represented by SIN).

SIN, INLE and ICOM participate in the **regular WG meetings** where they have the opportunity to exchange information and mutual learnings on encountered barriers, implemented innovations and best practices with the other BRIDGE projects as well as be informed about the status of BRIDGE activities and expected contributions from projects.

INLE and SIN participated remotely to the **annual BRIDGE General Assembly** where the annual results of the initiative are presented and the planning for the next year is presented to all projects.

In Year 2, PEDvolution actively contributed to a number of **BRIDGE activities** as described in Table 5Table 5.

Table 5: PEDvolution contribution to BRIDGE activities.

BRIDGE WG	BRIDGE activity	Partners
Regulation	Report on energy sharing (February 2025)	PED Managers and supporting teams (SWW, ESG, EG, WIN) and the Coordinator (INLE)
	Survey for E-handbook on key innovations and technological progress (February 2025)	PED Managers and supporting teams (SWW, ESG, EG) and the Coordinator (INLE)
	Survey on Regulatory and Consumer aspects in Energy Sharing	PED Manager (WIN)

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

BRIDGE WG	BRIDGE activity	Partners
	(March 2025)	
	Survey on Sector coupling/sector integration (September 2025)	Solution providers (OFFSET, ICOM)
	Survey on coordination of flexibility acquisition mechanisms (October 2025)	PED Managers (SWW, WIN, EG)
Data Management	Survey to gather insights from the BRIDGE projects on topics pertinent to the WG six active Actions (October 2025)	ICOM, TUW, OFFSET
Business Models	Survey and registration to provide insight for Task 1: Investigating the tools for capturing business ideas and building BM (Handbook) (Oct/Nov 2025)	SIN
	Survey input for BRIDGE General Assembly 2025 Report - Bridging the gap between innovation and the market	SIN
Consumer and Citizen Engagement	Contribution to the workshop “AI and engagement” (January 2025)	SIN
	Contribution to the Citizen and Consumer Engagement Annual Report 2025 on generic engagement topics, especially AI and engagement	SIN
	Fill in the general project survey on consumer and citizen engagement (November 2025)	SIN

5.2.1.2 ETIP SNET

INLE maintains close engagement with the activities of ETIP SNET WG2 on Storage Technologies and System Flexibilities through regular participation in WG meetings. This alignment offers a timely platform to channel project results into EU-level strategic guidance and to reinforce PEDvolution’s visibility within the broader energy systems community. In 2025, WG2’s flagship publication centred on District Storage, offering key insights and recommendations on district energy storage systems, their

strategic role in achieving EU goals and call to action for stakeholders. Building on this momentum, PEDvolution is positioned to contribute to the WG2 publication planned for 2026, showcasing PEDvolution’s insights on ongoing research on integrated storage solutions, flexibility services, and positive energy district strategies.

5.2.1.3 *Annex 83 Meetings*

ZHAW represented PEDvolution in the bi-weekly Subtask D “Demos, implementation and dissemination” Coordinators meeting with the aim to exchange information and mutual learnings on experiences, implemented innovations and best practices with other projects as well as for clustering and notification of other projects about PEDvolution activities such as the list of performance indicators for PEDs.

Partners from ZAHW and VITO provided inputs to the report “Demonstration cases on Positive Energy Districts and Related Technologies” drafted as part of the Annex83 and finalised in March 2025.

5.2.1.4 *COST Action PED-EU-NET*

PEDvolution further benefitted from the final results of the COST Action PED EU-NET that were released in early 2025. A number of high-quality PED-EU-NET deliverables were considered in the work on the PEDvolution KPIs, PED RA framework development, and monitoring strategy, namely:

[Deliverable 2.5 Report on Graph-Based Framework for Positive Energy Districts: Integrating KPIs, Tools, Stakeholder Roles, and Intervention Strategies](#)

[Deliverable 3.2: Report on PED Labs characterisation and KPIs](#)

[Deliverable 3.5 Devise the concept of a virtual PED Lab for demonstrating new technologies and solutions \(Concept on the development of a virtual PED Lab\)](#)

5.2.1.5 *Scalable Cities Community*

PEDvolution interacted with the Scalable Cities initiative in numerous ways.

INLE represented PEDvolution in the regular **Board of Coordinators** meeting with the aim to exchange information and mutual learnings on encountered barriers, implemented innovations and best practices with other projects as well as for clustering and notification of other projects about PEDvolution activities such as the Open Call for demonstrators.

Partners from ICOM and VITO provided inputs to the **report “From data to decisions: Key lessons from the SCC project”** drafted as part of the Scalable Cities Task Group on Monitoring and Evaluation and finalised in August 2025. Contributions are:

- *Chapter 3.7.5 Data sharing in the PEDvolution project* (provided by ICOM)
- *Example #2: Data-driven district energy planning with Urban Digital Twins: Lessons from the PEDvolution project* in chapter 4.2.4 Visualisation and communication interfaces (provided by VITO)

The City of Winterthur (WIN), one of the project’s three co-developer PEDs, represented PEDvolution as a visiting city at the **5th Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Workshop** in Barcelona on March 27-28, 2025. The workshop was co-organised by GNE Finance, Barcelona City Council, and the cities of Dijon, Bristol, Lund, and Leuven in the framework of Scalable Cities. As a PEDvolution PED, the City of Winterthur was

invited to present its approach to innovative legal frameworks and financial strategies for energy transition and climate protection (Figure 16). Their insights contributed to critical discussions on:

- Unlocking private investment for urban decarbonisation
- Bridging the gap between public entities and private investors
- Leveraging Smart Cities initiatives for data-driven decision-making

Figure 16: Presentation of the Winterthur PED (WIN) at the 5th SCC Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Workshop in Barcelona.

Additional interactions with the Scalable Cities Community through conferences (ChangeNOW and Cities Mission Conference) are described in [Section 5.1.4](#) of this report.

4.2.2.2 Plan 4 EU AI

PEDvolution was represented by TUW at the “Workshop on European AI Foundation Model for Energy Grids” held in Brussels on December 8, 2025. The workshop was organised by the European Commission (DG ENER B.4 – Digitalisation, Competitiveness & Technology), with the support of Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEF) and AI Factory representatives (RWTH Aachen/Fraunhofer FIT, INESC TEC and NTUA).

The workshop aimed at aligning multiple stakeholders (TSOs, DSOs, Research Institutes) to create the requirements needed to drive the development of a Foundation Model that can enable coordinated decision-making across grid operations, from real-time balancing to strategic planning.

TUW contributed to the workshop by sharing insights gained from their work on advanced reinforcement learning algorithms within PEDvolution. These insights informed the discussion on which modelling

approaches could be leveraged for the Foundation Model and how appropriate benchmarks can be established.

5.2.2 Liaison with standardisation activities

PEDvolution interacts with a number of standardisation groups including de jure EU standardisation bodies. The main interactions for Year 2 are described below.

5.2.2.1 CEN/TC 465

PEDvolution became Liaison Project with CEN/TC 465 – Sustainable Cities and Communities in December 2025.

Through participation in the Technical Committee PEDvolution will have the possibility to propose technical documents with a view of their possible conversion into CEN or CENELEC deliverables, have the possibility to introduce preparatory work as a support to ongoing standardisation activities, as well as to submit technical contributions to the body.

On the other hand, the PEDvolution project will benefit from knowledge gained on state-of-the-art developments on Sustainable Cities and Communities.

5.2.2.2 FLEXCOMMUNITY

The project participates in the FlexOffer User Group of FlexCommunity through OFFSET.

Key benefits include the sharing of the experiences of various members- solution providers to improve the functionality of the flexibility trading/exchange both in closed communities behind the meter and in the markets in front of the meter.

PEDvolution uses the FlexOffer protocol as the core standard for flexibilities exchange. It is the main language for WP5 (PED Energy Manager), but it extends also in WP7 (Data Exchange, Integration and Interoperability Platform). The extension for sector coupling (see list below) was identified bottom-up as part of the work in WP5, and concrete extension was proposed and put forward into the FlexOffer user group for synchronisation, visibility and co-development.

Project contribution (OFFSET):

- Preparation of rules for maturity of FlexOffer specification
- Coordination and participation in the Working group for establishing and tracking the reliability of Flexoffer
- Coordination and participation in the working group on cross-sector coupling Flexoffer specification

In addition, INLE participated in the FlexOffer User Group meeting #16 (24.4.2025) with a slot for "Projects using FlexOffer" where it had the chance to present how Flexoffer is used in PEDvolution (PED Energy manager and PED Interoperability Platform) and communicate the upcoming launch of the PEDvolution Open Call for Demonstrators.

5.2.2.3 AIOTI

INLE actively monitors the activities of the AIOTI Working Groups on Testing and Experimentation Environments (WG T&E) and Energy (WG Energy), participating in their meetings and tracking

publications and initiatives relevant to PEDvolution. Looking ahead, PEDvolution is expected to provide targeted contributions to AIOTI in Year 3 of the project, once robust results from the demonstration activities become available.

5.2.3 Liaison with other EU projects

PEDvolution maintains a broad network of EU projects focused on Positive Energy Districts. During its second year, the project co-organised and participated in several joint events with other PED-related EU projects, as outlined in this section.

5.2.3.1 Positive Energy Neighbourhoods and Districts Cluster

PEDvolution participated in CINEA “Positive Energy Neighbourhoods and District” cluster meeting that took place in Brussels on September 29th. PEDvolution was represented in the meeting by partners WIN and VITO (Figure 18). The three sister projects (**InterPED**, **HARMONISE**, PEDvolution) gave a joint presentation on «Interoperability - energy systems integration» with the results already achieved by the each of the projects (Figure 18).

This cluster allowed PEDvolution to exchange information and updates with similar projects, present and discuss the PED results and innovations and related challenges addressed by current research and demonstration actions, explore how the results from projects can be presented, shared, scaled up and replicated and identify collaboration opportunities.

It was also highly valuable to learn from and share experiences with other consortia across several breakout sessions, not only on the technical dimension of PED implementation, but also on business model innovations and stakeholder-engagement approaches. These aspects are essential to ensure that solutions are understood, embraced and deployed at scale across Europe.

During the discussions, partners also exchanged insights on several recurring topics that influence PED realisation in practice, including:

- The complexity of local governance structures and how responsibilities are often spread across many stakeholders.
- Regulatory considerations around STOA-type solutions, such as energy communities.
- Approaches to securing financing for replication beyond initial pilot districts, especially under current energy price conditions.
- Strategies to overcome data silos and improve interoperability between digital tools.
- Ways to strengthen collaboration across sectors such as energy, mobility, ICT and buildings.
- The importance of anticipating system flexibility needs and grid interaction, illustrated by experiences where battery business cases were affected by local grid constraints.

Other participating projects were: H2020-LC-SC3-2019-ES-SCC: Smart Cities and Communities (**ATELIER**, **POCITYF**, **RESPONSE**); H2020-LC-GD-4-1-2020: Building and renovating in an energy and resource efficient way (**ARV**, **oPEN LAB**, **PROBONO**); HORIZON-MISS-2021-CIT-02-04: Positive Clean Energy Districts (**ASCEND**, **NEUTRALPATH**); HORIZON-MISS-2023-CIT-01-02: Positive clean energy district (PED) digital twins – from modelling to creating climate neutral Cities (**BIPED**, **EXPEDITE**, **TIPS4PED**).

Figure 17: PEDvolution team (WIN, VITO) at the CINEA cluster meeting in Brussels.

Figure 18: Joint presentation of PEDvolution and sister projects at the CINEA cluster meeting in Brussels.

5.2.3.2 *Joint Workshop on PED Innovation and Collaboration*

PEDvolution, with efforts from INLE, SXS and SIN, co-organised the workshop “Building the Future of Energy: A Joint Workshop on PED Innovation and Collaboration”² together with four leading EU PED projects (**HARMONISE**, **InterPED**, **ASCEND**, and **NEUTRALPATH**) in an interactive exchange hosted by the Scalable Cities Initiative. The event took place online on June 19, 2025.

INLE presented PEDvolution (Figure 20) and SIN led the thematic panel discussion on Community engagement & social innovation with knowledge gained from PEDvolution (Figure 19).

The workshop offered a shared understanding of how PEDs take shape across Europe, highlighting diverse strategies, from digital platforms to inclusive governance. Common challenges and clear

² <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7341736615167365121/>

synergies emerged, paving the way for knowledge sharing, peer support and deeper collaboration ahead. The full discussion is available at the recording [here](#).

Figure 19: Thematic panel (led by SIN) on Community engagement & social innovation with knowledge gained from PEDvolution at the joint Building the Future of Energy workshop.

Figure 20: PEDvolution presentation (INLE) at the at the joint Building the Future of Energy workshop.

5.3 Capacity Building Activities from PED Co-Developers to Follower PEDs

The evaluation and selection process of the follower PEDs was concluded in November 2025 and the awarded PEDs are currently in the contracting phase. As soon as the contracts are in place, the Onboarding Phase aiming at the preparation of the follower PEDs for the demonstration phase of the project will commence. Onboarding consists of the following steps:

1. Familiarisation with Project Tools and Resources

- Attend onboarding/capacity-building sessions to understand the PEDvolution tools (e.g., PED Energy Manager, Digital Twin, Interoperability Platform).
- Review technical and financial support resources provided by the consortium.
- Participate in initial coordination meetings with solution providers and existing PEDs.

2. Baseline Data Collection

- Gather and validate pre-project energy, emissions, and community engagement baseline data, and any other relevant information.
- Conduct site-specific discussions to determine existing infrastructure and potential constraints for data and assets.
- Share collected data with the consortium for initial assessments.
- Develop a timeline for implementing proposed solutions.

3. Co-development planning

- Collaborate with the consortium to finalise the demonstration phase plan.
- Define specific project goals, including energy efficiency targets, renewable energy integration, and community engagement.

Capacity building is part of the **Familiarisation with Project Tools and Resources** and it aims to contribute to the swift and smooth preparation of the follower PEDs for the demonstrations taking place in WP9 (PEDvolution demonstrators and performance assessment). Knowledge will be shared from all actors of the project including co-developer PEDs, solution providers and leaders of deployment and demonstration activities.

The draft agenda for the kick-off meeting is detailed below. A tentative date has been planned for the second half of January 2026.

Table 6: Onboarding of follower PEDs – Kick of meeting draft agenda.

Duration / total	Partner	Content
10 min	INLE	Project overview (project objectives, project status, co-developer PEDs, planned capacity building and onboarding activities) incl. expectations for C&D&E activities
10 min / newcomer (30 min)	Newcomers	PED presentation (<i>content to be proposed by solution providers and WP8 and WP9 leaders</i>)
10 min	SWW	What newcomer PEDs are expected to do/provide in WP9
10 min	ESG	What newcomer PEDs are expected to do/provide in WP8 + detailed next steps
30 min	All	Q&A
10 min / solution (90 min)	Solution providers	Pitch. Testing requirements. 1 slide dedicated to each of the newcomers
10 min / co-developer (30 min)	WIN, GEK, SWW	Deployment planning and status

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

30 min	All	Q&A
--------	-----	-----

Following the kick-off meeting where all follower PEDs and PEDvolution partners will participate, a number of dedicated follower PEDs workshops will be organised addressing the **Baseline Data Collection** and **Co-development planning** activities of the onboarding phase. The agendas for the respective workshops will be determined by the solution providers and leaders of deployment and demonstration activities.

6 KPIs OVERVIEW AND PROGRESS

During year 2, PEDvolution's communication and dissemination activities continued to be closely monitored against project KPIs, playing a central role in assessing outreach impact, and overall progress. The internal dedicated monitoring and tracking tool ([Annex II](#)) developed in year 1, remained essential for supporting accurate and consistent reporting across all consortium partners. Updated regularly under the guidance of SXS, the tool facilitated continuous input of data, ensuring that all C&D&E contributions were captured in a timely and structured manner.

Fully aligned with the Horizon Europe reporting platform, the tool ensured smooth transfer of information for CINEA reporting requirements. The separate reporting tabs -covering Communication activities, Dissemination activities, Scientific Publications, Popularised Publications, Liaison with EU-initiatives and Liaison with EU-projects- continued to serve as the backbone for structured data collection and quality assurance.

To maintain coherence with the project's progress and increase visibility around performance trends, Year 2 was guided by a specific set of annual KPIs complementing the overall project KPIs defined in the Grant Agreement. As presented in [Table 7](#), the status reflects strong progress across indicators.

The compiled information for Year 2 shows that the majority of KPIs have been met or are on track, with several already surpassing expectations due to the intensified dissemination efforts and the growing availability of public project results. With PEDvolution entering its more results-oriented phase, engagement with external stakeholders increased significantly, further reinforcing outreach and visibility, and is expected to be intensified further with integration of the new follower PEDs (resulting from the Open Call for Demonstrators), and the initiation of the demonstration phase (year 3). This positive trajectory suggests that the project's C&D&E strategy is effectively supporting the broader objectives and contributing to a stronger presence among EU-level energy, digitalisation and PED communities.

A notable development during this year was the expansion of liaison and standardisation activities, which are gaining increasing importance as project results emerge. Notably, the project established a liaison with CEN/TC 465 "Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities", creating a direct channel for contributing to ongoing European standardisation activities. This engagement positions PEDvolution to actively inform emerging standards from the coming year onward, while ensuring that its outputs and methodologies, remain fully aligned with future European frameworks and interoperable across diverse urban contexts. This step marks an important milestone in the project's ambition to support long-term replicability and interoperability across Europe.

Particularly noteworthy this year were the significant growth of the PEDvolution LinkedIn page, the increased participation of partners in third-party (particularly EU level) events, and the significant progress in scientific publications early on. However, challenges remain regarding the pace of follower growth on the X (Twitter) account - which is being addressed via the integration of the Bluesky account but also foreseen to be significantly improved during the demonstration phase where pilot site participants will be directly engaged in project activities. The number of report downloads has also increased significantly, despite the limited public results available to date, indicating an increasing interest from expert target groups. The PEDvolution Zenodo account has also contributed towards this direction, particularly since it is part of the *EU Open Research Repository community*, which makes public material available to a wide range of relevant stakeholders.

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

Overall, partners demonstrated strong engagement during Year 2, contributing to a robust set of C&D&E activities. As the project enters its most results-intensive phases, maintaining close cooperation with the C&D&E Manager and ensuring consistent reporting will be essential. This will help sustain momentum, maximise outreach, and reinforce the project’s impact across EU networks, stakeholder communities and policy-related initiatives.

Table 7: KPIs and Year 2 Cumulative Status.

INDICATOR	TARGET (PROJECT DURATION)	TARGET (YEAR 2)	YEAR 2 (STATUS)
Website unique visitors*	>10000	>5500	5730
Website page views*	>30000	>15000	17660
Report downloads*	>8000	>3300	3488
Video views*	>2000	>500	373
Project outreach contacts*	>2000	>1200	7336
Posts to digital hubs*	>10	>6	4
Social networks original posts*	>100	>60	103
LinkedIn followers*	>500	>300	755
Twitter followers*	>1000	>600	200
Representation in EU events*	>3	>2	22
Representation in national/regional events*	>5	>2	8
Final conference participants*	>120	-	-
News Alerts Recipients*	>1000	>700	143
News Alerts Issues*	>6	>4	6
News Alerts Open Rate*	30%	>30%	46%
PEDvolution Scientific publications*	>5	>2	3

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

INDICATOR	TARGET (PROJECT DURATION)	TARGET (YEAR 2)	YEAR 2 (STATUS)
Other Thematically relevant publications from PEDvolution partners	-	-	3
LinkedIn total impressions**	-	-	118 499
LinkedIn unique visitors**	-	-	689
LinkedIn total views**	-	-	2827
LinkedIn original posts**	-	-	103
X(Twitter) original posts**	-	-	99
Bluesky followers**	-	-	144
YouTube channel subscribers**	-	-	5
Brochures printed**	-	-	>500
Liaison with EU initiatives**	-	-	9
Liaison with EU projects**	-	-	19

* KPI as defined in the GA and D10.1.

** Additional KPIs – Year 2 status.

7 UPDATED WORKPLAN

WP12 “Project Communication, Dissemination and Further Exploitation (Year 3)” advances the actions initiated in earlier phases and places a stronger emphasis on maximising the exploitation of PEDvolution results. Alongside completing ongoing communication, dissemination, and liaison activities, WP12 focuses on ensuring that project outcomes are positioned for uptake, replication, and long-term impact. The work in WP12 is guided by three core objectives:

1. Accelerate the uptake of PEDvolution results through active stakeholder, end-user, and citizen engagement supported by agile communication and dissemination.
2. Conduct benchmarking, barriers assessment, and liaison activities to draw on insights from PEDvolution PEDs and external PEDs across Europe and beyond.
3. Develop targeted exploitation strategies, supported by qualification activities, replication planning, and market analysis.

WP12 consists of three main tasks, each addressing a distinct dimension of communication, dissemination, and exploitation objectives, as shown in [Figure 22](#), together with their respective Lead Beneficiaries.

Figure 21: PEDvolution WP12 – Gantt Chart – Work Plan overview.

T12.1: COMMUNICATION OF THE PROJECT AND DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS

The implementation of PEDvolution’s communication and dissemination activities, aiming to maximise the visibility and impact of the project’s results will be continued during its final year. The activities will focus on engaging stakeholders at EU, national, and local levels, while ensuring the project’s outputs are accessible, widely shared, and effectively exploited.

EU Dissemination Events and Networks – Final Conference: Building on Year 2 activities, PEDvolution will participate in at least one EU-level event in Year 3. Additionally, at least two more scientific publications are planned. During the last three months of the project, PEDvolution will organise a physical final conference in Brussels to present major project findings at the EU level.

National Dissemination Events and Networks: As a continuation of Year 2 activities, PEDvolution partners will participate in at least three national-level dissemination events throughout Year 3. These activities will support outreach to regional stakeholders, policymakers, industry, research communities, and the public, fostering knowledge exchange, collaboration, and awareness of project outcomes across partner countries.

Project Online Presence Updates: The project’s digital presence will be further enhanced via the website, News Alerts, social media channels (LinkedIn, X, Bluesky, YouTube), and relevant digital hubs. Updates will be provided regularly throughout Year 3 to ensure ongoing engagement with stakeholders, timely dissemination of results, and promotion of project activities to a broad audience.

Other Communication Material – Layman’s Report: A Layman’s Report will be produced in English, to summarise PEDvolution’s results in a clear, user-friendly format. This report will target non-expert audiences, ensuring that the project’s key messages, outcomes, and practical impacts are accessible to citizens, policymakers, and the wider public.

T12.2 LIAISON WITH BRIDGE AND OTHER EU INITIATIVES

Building on the liaison activities initiated in the previous years, activities will be continued in Year 3 with a distinctly increased importance as project public results, evidence, and validated outputs become available for broader dissemination. This expanded knowledge base will enable PEDvolution to intensify its engagement with BRIDGE and other relevant EU initiatives.

Throughout the year, the project will present the testing and validation results of the PED-RA to these platforms, supporting EU-level policy discussions with real-world insights and strengthening alignment with ongoing energy transition initiatives. These interactions will further contribute to refining the PED-RA, exploring its standardisation potential, and enhancing opportunities for replication across Europe.

T12.3 SUSTAINABILITY PLAN, EXPLOITATION AND REPLICATION

Joint and Individual Exploitation Strategy for Key Exploitable Results: Coordinated and partner-specific exploitation strategies will be developed for the most promising Key Exploitable Results (KERs). Building on the updated KER list and their characterisation from T11.2, SXS will guide partners through a structured process of prioritisation and needs assessment, considering each KER’s exploitation potential, partner intentions, and the established IPR framework. The outcome will be a coherent set of joint and individual exploitation pathways that maximise uptake and value creation. As PEDvolution

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

begins releasing public results, this activity becomes increasingly critical for strengthening partner alignment, accelerating market readiness, and intensifying liaison efforts with external stakeholders.

Replication and Market Analysis: The replication potential and market relevance of PEDvolution solutions will be further elaborated across diverse district contexts. The work will follow the following four steps:

1. identifying key success criteria for implementing PEDvolution solutions in PEDs, near-PED districts, and other urban settings
2. developing a dataset of these criteria across district typologies, addressing data gaps through literature review, expert assumptions, and uncertainty analysis
3. assessing the future evolution of these criteria using building-stock scenarios and modelling approaches; and
4. analysing replication potential and expected impacts on key indicators such as GHG emissions, energy demand, and economic performance (D12.2).

With newly available project outcomes and public deliverables, this analysis becomes even more impactful, enabling stronger outreach, evidence-based liaison with cities, and more confident replication planning.

Finally, all partners will continue to update the Monitoring and Tracking tool, to closely monitor activities and ensure the consortium is working efficiently towards achieving the defined C&D&E objectives as foreseen by the project’s GA.

[Figure 23](#) below, presents a detailed breakdown of each planned C&D&E task for Phase 3 of the project. As a result of the above tasks, the following public deliverables are foreseen to be developed by the end of the project:

- D12.1 “Communication and dissemination activities - year 3”
- D12.2 “PEDvolution replication and market analysis & exploitation strategy”

	2026											
	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
WP12: Project Communication, Dissemination and further Exploitation (Year 3) (M25-M36)	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36
Communication of the project and Dissemination of results - Year 3 (M25-36)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D
<i>EU dissemination events and networks – Final Conference (SXS/ ALL)</i>												
<i>Participation in EU dissemination event</i>												
<i>Final Conference</i>												
<i>4 Scientific Publications</i>												
<i>National dissemination events and networks (SXS/ ALL)</i>												
<i>Project online presence updates (SXS/ ALL)</i>												
<i>Website updates</i>												
<i>News Alerts</i>												

D11.1. Communication and dissemination activities – Year 2

<i>Social media account updates</i>													
<i>Hub updates</i>													
<i>Other communication material - Layman's report (SXS)</i>													
Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M25-36)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	
<i>Liaison with BRIDGE and other EU initiatives (M25-36) (INLE, VTIQ, SN, ICOM, ZHAW, SWW, BSC)</i>													
Sustainability plan, exploitation and replication (M25-M36)	J	F	M	A	M	J	J	A	S	O	N	D	
<i>Joint and Individual exploitation strategy for most promising KERs (SXS/ALL)</i>													
<i>Replication and market analysis (TUW)</i>													
<i>Identification of key success criteria</i>													
<i>Set-up a database</i>													
<i>Assess possible evolution of criteria</i>													
<i>Assess potential to replicate PED solution solutions</i>													

Figure 22: PEDvolution Year 3 C&D&E activities – detailed Work Plan.

8 CONCLUSION

The Year 2 C&D&E activities were successfully delivered, with steady progress across all tasks and strong performance against KPIs. PEDvolution continues to expand its outreach and strengthen engagement with diverse audiences, providing a solid foundation for the next period, when the project's key results will be consolidated, communicated, and increasingly exploited.

Consortium collaboration has remained productive and well-coordinated, supporting the effective implementation of communication, dissemination, and liaison actions. As the project enters the more results-driven phase 3, maintaining frequent and structured communication will be essential to uphold momentum and ensure timely, high-quality delivery.

More specifically, during Year 2, PEDvolution further consolidated its communication channels and strengthened its online presence, enabling enhanced visibility and regular dissemination of project progress. Importantly, liaison activities have increased in relevance and depth, supported by the emergence of public project results and overall project progress. Engagement with EU initiatives such as BRIDGE has intensified, and cooperation with relevant EU projects and networks has expanded and further strengthened. In parallel, PEDvolution established a liaison with CEN/TC 465 "Sustainable and Smart Cities and Communities", positioning the project to contribute to future European standardisation efforts.

The activities planned for year 3 will be critical for maximising the project's overall impact, particularly in terms of targeted dissemination, exploitation, and replication. The development of robust joint and individual exploitation strategies during phase 3 will be especially important, ensuring that the project's KERs can be effectively taken up, replicated, and positioned for long-term sustainability beyond the project's duration. Building on the solid foundation established during the first two years, the project is now well-placed to accelerate outreach, foster deeper stakeholder involvement, and ensure that its results are communicated, valorised, and leveraged effectively throughout the remainder of the project.

9 REFERENCES

- [1] M. Haase, “Entschlüsselung des Dekarbonierungsprozesses von Quartieren aus Betreiber- und FM-Sicht,” in *SPOTLIGHT FMplus – Facility Management Fachkonferenz: Wissenschaft und Praxis im Dialog*, Tagungsband, Zürich, Switzerland, 30–31 Jan. 2025.
- [2] M. Haase and S. Ashworth, “Best Practices of PEDs and its Replication Potential,” in *REAL CORP 2025 Proceedings/Tagungsband*, 14–16 Apr. 2025.
- [3] M. Sharifi, A. Kouti, M. H. Shamsi, R. Guo, and D. Saelens, “Propagating epistemic uncertainties in planning and design of energy efficient districts,” *Sustainable Cities and Society*, vol. 130, p. 106520, Jul. 2025.
- [4] A. Conte, V. Carabias, L. Berzi, P. Kienast, and M. Delogu, “Positive energy district evolution: A test case for Winterthur's Hard Community,” *Journal of Smart Cities and Society*, vol. 4, no. 3, 2025.
- [5] “CLIMA World Congress,” *CLIMA World Congress*, [Online]. Available: <https://climaworldcongress.org>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [6] “Program at a Glance – CLIMA 2025,” *CLIMA World Congress*, [Online]. Available: https://climaworldcongress.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Program-at-a-Glance-CLIMA-2025_LR.pdf. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [7] “C4E Forum 2025 Post-Conference Booklet,” *C4E Forum*, [Online]. Available: <https://c4eforum.net/c4e-forum2025-post-conference-booklet/>. [Accessed: Dec. 2025].
- [8] “IEWT 2025,” 14th International Energy Economics Conference, [Online]. Available: <https://iewt2025.org>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [9] “IFMA CH – International Facility Management Association,” [Online]. Available: <https://www.ifma.ch/>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [10] “ChangeNow Conference,” *ChangeNow*, [Online]. Available: <https://www.changenow.world/>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [11] “Cities Mission Conference,” *Net Zero Cities*, [Online]. Available: <https://netzerocities.eu/cities-mission-conference/>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [12] “The PEDvolution consortium meets in Kranj, Slovenia,” *Sympraxis*, [Online]. Available: <https://sympraxis.eu/cms/the-pedvolution-consortium-meets-in-kranj-slovenia/>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [13] “The PEDvolution consortium meets in Kranj, Slovenia,” *es-geht GmbH*, [Online]. Available: <https://es-geht.gmbh/the-pedvolution-consortium-meets-in-kranj-slovenia/>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [14] “PEDvolution Open Call for Demonstrators – Co-Creating Europe’s Positive Energy Districts!,” *Smart Cities Marketplace*, [Online]. Available: <https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/news-and-events/news/2025/joint-scalable-cities-smart-cities-marketplace-roadshow-peer-peer-session>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [15] “PEDvolution and oPEN Lab: Joint Presence at C4E Forum 2025,” *Sympraxis*, [Online]. Available: <https://sympraxis.eu/cms/pedvolution-and-open-lab-joint-presence-at-c4e-forum-2025/>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].
- [16] “Scalable Cities Roadshow: How to Deploy Innovative Financial Strategies,” *Smart Cities Marketplace*, [Online]. Available: <https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/news-and-events/news/2025/scalable-cities-roadshow-how-deploy-innovative-financial-strategies>. [Accessed: Nov. 2025].

Annex I: NEWS ALERT ISSUES

MAY 2025 ISSUES

News Alert Topic: Open Call Launch

PEDvolution Breaking News Alert
1 message

Sympraxis <mail@sendfoxmail.com> 9 May 2025 at 11:31
Reply-To: Sympraxis <admin@sympraxis.eu>
To:

BREAKING NEWS ALERT

PEDvolution has officially launched its Open Call for Positive Energy District (PED) Demonstrators — Apply now

Deadline: 30 June 2025

Open call for Positive Energy District (PED) demonstrators

 Co-funded by the European Union
Co-funded by the European Union under agreements of 101184723. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or COMENIUS for Europe. It does not imply any endorsement or approval by the European Union.
 Swiss Government
Swiss Government
Department of Economic Affairs, Education and Research (SEM)
State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)
Swiss Confederation
The Swiss project contributes received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

🌍 Ready to take your neighbourhood, district, or city to the next level? 🚀

Whether you are operating, implementing, expanding, designing, or planning a Positive Energy District (PED) in your area — the moment is **here!**

News Alert Topic: Open Call & Joint Online Workshop

PEDvolution News Alert

1 message

Sympraxis <mail@sendfoxmail.com>
Reply-To: Sympraxis <admin@sympraxis.eu>
To:

30 May 2025 at 14:33

NEWS ALERT

👋 Join us for an informative online workshop on Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)

Save the Date — Registration is Now Open

An illustration for a workshop poster. At the top, there are logos for ASCEND, NEUTRALPATH, INTERPED, PEDvolution, and HARMONISE. Below the logos, four stylized human figures are shown in a meeting setting: one standing on the left, two sitting at a table, and one standing on the right. The standing figure on the right is pointing to a sign that reads "Scalable Cities" and "PED Joint Workshop". The background shows a modern office or meeting room with a window and a lamp.

Building the Future of Energy
A Joint Workshop on
PED Innovation & Collaboration

June 11th, 2025 at 09:30-12:30 CET

 Funded by the European Union

JUNE 2025 ISSUE

News Alert Topic: 1st 2025 Bi-Annual Update

PEDvolution News Alert 2025a - June 2025
1 message

Sympraxis <mail@sendfoxmail.com> 1 July 2025 at 17:04
Reply-To: Sympraxis <admin@sympraxis.eu>
To:

NEWS ALERT 2025a

**Year 2 — Co-developing Interoperable Solutions for
Energy-Efficient & Sustainable Urban Districts Across
Europe**

June 2025

NOVEMBER 2025 ISSUE

News Alert Topic: 2nd 2025 Bi-Annual Update

PEDvolution Breaking News Alert | November 2025

1 message

Sympraxis <mail@sendfoxmail.com>
Reply-To: Sympraxis <admin@sympraxis.eu>
To:

5 November 2025 at 10:21

NEWS ALERT 2025b

**From Collaboration to Implementation Across Europe's
Positive Energy Districts**

November 2025

**PEDvolution launches its advertorial video — Discover how Europe's
districts can drive the energy transition!**

Annex II: MONITORING AND TRACKING TOOL

1. Communication activities								
Activity (Short label as described in communication, dissemination, exploitation plan)*	Title of activity	Date (dd/mm/year)	Place	Partner (short name)	Organisation (O) or Participation (P)	Link	Description*	Communication channel*
Conference	SGES	27-29/08/2024	Winterthur, Switzerland	ZHAW/WIN	P	https://sges.ch/swiss-green-economy-symposium-2024/	Presentation of the PEDvolution materials (brochure, poster) via the ZHAW stand	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
Scalable Cities Community Roadshow	Roadshow: Build your financial capacity - Nature, mobility and urban sustainability: European cities towards climate neutrality	14-15/07/2025	Athens, Greece	SXS	P	https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/news-and-events/news/2025/joint-scalable-cities-smart-cities-marketplace-roadshow-peer-peer-session	Networking with the representatives from EU cities, exchange of knowledge and experience on nature-based solutions and the potential impact of PEDs	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
Conference	Chair of PED session	5/6/2025	Milano, Italy	ZHAW	P	https://climaworldcongress.org	We organized a special session on PEDs. Positive energy districts and energy communities: case studies and applications towards the decarbonization of the built environment. We shared and discussed various insights from latest PED research.	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
Conference	EEM 25: Scientific Presentation	27-29/05/2025	Lisbon, Portugal	TUW	P	https://eem25.pt/	Presented research work done within the context of T5.1 in PEDvolution. Title: Reinforcement Learning-Based Charging Control in Households under Real-time Pricing	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
Conference	IEWT 2025: Scientific Presentation	26-28/02/2025	Vienna, Austria	TUW	P	https://iewt2025.eeg.tuwien.ac.at/	Presented research work done within the context of T5.1 in PEDvolution within the session "Endconsumers". Title: Reinforcement Learning-Based Charging Control in Households under Real-Time Pricing	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
Conference	45th IAEE Conference: Scientific Presentation	25-28/06/2024	Istanbul, Turkey	TUW	P	https://www.iaee2024.org.tr/	Presented research work done within the context of T2.3 in PEDvolution. Title: A Reinforcement Learning Approach for Optimal Household Battery Charging using Real-time Pricing	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)
Conference	SES 2024: Scientific Presentation	10-11/09/2024	Aalborg, Denmark	TUW	P	https://smartenergysystems.eu/2024-2	Presented research work done within the context of T3.2. Title: Optimizing District Heating for Positive Energy Districts	Event (conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.)